

Measuring quality of the Hazy image dependind on He-Ne Laser

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ABSTRACT

Determining the quality of the hazy image is difficult problem, thus these images need to analyzing after determined the quality or dehazing. In this paper, we analyzed the hazy (by the dust) images depending on $Y_C B_C R_C$ color space. First we designed the system captured images which graded for high to very low hazy (by adding the dust) by using He-Ne laser, due to it have low power, in these images we calculated the Normalize Mean Square error (NMSE) as a function of lase intensity for each components in $Y_C B_C R_C$ and RGB color space, and the basic components in the Structure Similarity Index (SSIM) are (contrast, structure and luminance) moreover the mean for all has been calculated. We can see the lightness (in $Y_C B_C R_C$) and luminance (in SSIM) component are not effected by the dust whereas the chromatic components are highly effected by the dust.

Keywords:-the hazy images, dehazing,Laser He-Ne, $Y_C B_C R_C$ color space

1.INTRODUCTION

Computer vision system can be used for many outdoor applications, such as video surveillance, remote sensing, and intelligent vehicles. Virtually all computer vision tasks or computational photography algorithms assume that the input images are taken in clear weather and robust feature detection are achieved in high quality image[1]. The irradiance received by the camera from the scene point is attenuated along the line of sight. Furthermore, the incoming light is blended with the air light[2]. Hazy image analysis it is important case in the dehazing image and image quality assessment. For example many search [1 ,3 ,4], included dehazing but not used objective quality assessments. where The image quality metrics can be broadly classified into two categories, subjective and objective. A large numbers of objective image quality metrics have been developed during the last decade. Objective metrics can be divided [5,6] in three categories: Full Reference, Reduced Reference and No Reference. In this paper, the hazy color images have been analyzed depending on two objectives quality are the SSIM and NMSR. The each component of $Y_C B_C R_C$ color space are employed in SSIM and NMSR and we compared between them, the important of this procedure is determine the quality of hazy image and the manner of it enhanced.in this search the intensity of HeNe laser had been used to measuring the quality of dust image depending on $Y_C B_C R_C$ color space and we attempt to answer the question "what is the component in $Y_C B_C R_C$ has more effective in hazy?".Moreover the components of SSIM in the lightness (Luminance structure and contrast)has been studied.

2. LASER HE-NE

The lasing medium in the He-Ne laser is a mixture of about 85% helium and 15% neon, with neon providing the lasing action. An energy level diagram for neon is shown in Figure (1).The four-level system of a gas laser differs from the three-level system of chromium in that the emission of a photon does not return the atom to a ground level. Transitions from level E3 to E4 and E4 to E1 are accomplished through phonon transitions in which energy is transferred mainly through heat.Pumping neon to an excited state is not accomplished directly by the energy source. Rather, indirect pumping is accomplished by exciting atoms of helium, which then transfer energy to the new atoms by way of electron collision. These two gases are picked because they have electron excitation levels that are almost identical, thus facilitating the necessary energy transfer. Additionally in the mixture of gases used, a population inversion in helium is not required in order to obtain a population inversion in neon. The He Ne gas mixture is contained in a sealed tube. Excitation of the helium is accomplished by discharging electricity through the tube, similar to a neon sign. The mirrors may be enclosed within the tube or may form the end caps of the tube containing the He Ne mixture. This is a solid geometrical configuration and results in a stable light output. Some specialized high performance applications require externally mounted mirrors and a delicate alignment procedure. When this is done, the ends of the laser tube are made of Pyrex or quartz set at a Brewster's angle to the axis of the laser, and the output is polarized the light is extremely monochromatic with wavelength = 632.8 nmB. Consequently, the light has high "temporal coherence", meaning as you travelalong the direction of propagation, the components of the electric fieldcontinue to oscillate like a sine-wave with a single wavelength, amplitude, andphase Of course, no light source generates perfect plane-waves. Real wave trainshave finite length. The distance over which the waveform remainssimilar to a sine-wave is called the coherence- length of the beam, L_c , and it istypically about 10-30 cm for commercial He-Ne lasers[7].

Figure 1 An energy level diagram for neon

In helium-neon lasers, the neon atoms are the source of laser light. Because stimulated emission only takes place when there are excited neon atoms available, the process will quickly come to an end unless the neon atoms are replenished with energy. The helium atoms in the laser gas carry out the process of re-energizing the neon. Helium is perfect for this task because it has a meta-stable state (does not decay as quickly) corresponding to the energy required to re-energize the neon. Therefore, not only do the helium atoms have the proper energy to re-energize the neon, they can hold onto that energy long enough to transfer it. The amount of radiation that the neon atoms can emit is insufficient to produce a powerful beam without using some form of amplification. Much like a light bulb, the photons in the laser gas travel in random directions making it impossible to create a focused beam. The randomness of the photon paths also makes the laser inefficient because many photons may escape the tube before stimulating further emission. This problem is solved by placing mirrors at either end of the laser tube. Although many photons continue to escape the tube without being productive, those photons that are emitted parallel to the axis between the mirrors will be reflected many times. Each time the photons are reflected through the laser gas, they can cause more photons to be emitted in the same direction. In a short period of time, the dominant direction of emission will be along the axis between the mirrors. In standard configurations, one of the mirrors is totally reflective while the other can transmit one percent of all incident light. The beam is formed by the photons that escape through the partially transparent mirror. While not the most powerful or efficient laser, the helium-neon laser has many advantages over other types of lasers. Most lasers have an efficiency of about 1 percent, about ten times the efficiency of the typical helium-neon laser. Most lasers are capable of delivering power far in excess of the helium-neon laser's 75 milliwatt limit. The advantages of helium-neon lasers are that they can emit visible light, are affordable and have good beam quality. While most lasers cannot efficiently emit visible light, helium-neon lasers usually emit at 632.8nm, producing a red beam. Helium-neon lasers do not require any consumables (sapphire rods or cryogenic gases for example), nor do they generate enough heat to require special cooling devices. They also have good beam quality, that is, their beams stay tightly focused even over long distances. Helium-neon lasers are versatile devices that have many useful applications. They are often found in integrated bar code readers (the hand-held bar code readers use red semiconductor lasers or red LEDs.) Because they can emit visible light, helium-neon lasers are used in laser surgery to position the powerful infrared cutting beams. Surveyors take advantage of the helium-neon laser's good beam quality to take precise measurements over long distances or across inaccessible terrain. Red helium-neon lasers are also used in holography[8].

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of a helium–neon laser

3. YC_BC_R COLOR SPACE

In the area of digital video, which is increasingly gaining importance, the internationally standardized YC_BC_R color space is employed for the representation of color vectors. This color space differs from the color space used in analog video recording, which will not be gone into at this point. A detailed description of digital and analog video technology is included in [9]. The values in the R_NG_NB_N color space can be transformed into the values in the YC_BC_R color space [9]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} Y \\ C_B \\ C_R \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 16 \\ 128 \\ 128 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{1}{256} \begin{pmatrix} 65.738 & 129.057 & 25.064 \\ -37.945 & -74.494 & 112.439 \\ 112.439 & -94.154 & -18.285 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} R_N \\ G_N \\ B_N \end{pmatrix} \tag{1}$$

From this transformation it is assumed that the RGB data has already undergone a gamma correction. The quantities for the Y components refer to the fixed values for phosphors in the reference Rec. ITU-R BT.601-4 of the NTSC system. The back transformation from the YC_BC_R color space into the R_NG_NB_N color space is (except for a few rounding errors) given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} R_N \\ G_N \\ B_N \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{256} \begin{pmatrix} 298.082 & 0.0 & 408.583 \\ 298.082 & -100.291 & -208.120 \\ 298.082 & 516.411 & 0.0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Y - 16 \\ C_B - 128 \\ C_R - 128 \end{pmatrix} \tag{2}$$

[9,10]. The YC_BC_R color space was developed for representations in the television format common until now. It does not apply to the HDTV (high definition television) format [10].

4. IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT

The SSIM metric is based on the evaluation of three different measures, the luminance, contrast, and structure comparison measures are computed as [11]:

$$l(x, y) = \frac{2\mu_X(x, y)\mu_Y(x, y) + C_1}{\mu_X^2(x, y) + \mu_Y^2(x, y) + C_1} \tag{3}$$

$$c(x, y) = \frac{2\sigma_X(x, y)\sigma_Y(x, y) + C_2}{\sigma_X^2(x, y) + \sigma_Y^2(x, y) + C_2} \tag{4}$$

$$s(x, y) = \frac{\sigma_{XY}(x, y) + C_3}{\sigma_X(x, y)\sigma_Y(x, y) + C_3} \tag{5}$$

Where **X** and **Y** correspond to two different images that we would like to match, i.e. two different blocks in two separate images, μ_x , σ_x^2 , and σ_{xy} the mean of **X**, the variance of **X**, and the covariance of **X** and **Y** respectively where [11]:

$$\mu(x, y) = \sum_{p=-P}^P \sum_{q=-Q}^Q w(p, q) X(x + p, y + q) \tag{6}$$

$$\sigma^2(x, y) = \sum_{p=-P}^P \sum_{q=-Q}^Q w(p, q) [X(x + p, y + q) - \mu_X(x, y)]^2 \tag{7}$$

$$Y(x + p, y + q) - \mu_Y(x, y) \tag{8}$$

Where $w(p, q)$ is a Gaussian weighing function such that:

$$\sum_{p=-P}^P \sum_{q=-Q}^Q w(p, q) = 1 \tag{9}$$

And C_1, C_2 , and C_3 are constants given by $C_1 = (K_1L)^2$, $C_2 = (K_2L)^2$, and $C_3 = C_2/2$. L is the dynamic range for the sample data, i.e. $L = 255$ for 8 bit content and $K_1 \ll 1$ and $K_2 \ll 1$ are two scalar constants. In this study we used $K_1=0.01$ and $K_2=0.03$. Given the above measures the structural similarity can be computed as [11]:

$$SSIM(x, y) = [l(x, y)] \cdot [c(x, y)] \cdot [s(x, y)] \tag{10}$$

5. IMAGE DEGRAM MODEL

In image processing, the model widely used to describe the formation of a haze image is given by [3]

$$I(x) = J(x)t(x) + A(1 - t(x)) \quad (11)$$

A is the global atmospheric light, and t is medium transmission $J(x)$ is the original surface radiance vector at the intersection point of the scene with the real-world ray $J(x)t(x)$ is direct attenuation term[12], representing the scene radiation decay effect in the medium, $A(1 - t(x))$ is airlight term[2,12], describing the light scattering from atmosphere particles inducing color distortion. Direct attenuation describes the scene radiance and its decay in the medium, while airlight results from previously scattered light and leads to the shift of the scene color[12].

6. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

In this search a system has been designed to measure the amount of the haze (particle of dust), that is distorted the image. Figure(3) illustrated the measurement system which is made up of firm glass box, Fan, laser HeNe in figure(2), Camera stand, camera and Lux meter .The Fan is used to stir the dust that is putting in the box, in the same time the lux meter measured the laser intensity. When a specific amount of the dust is added in the box the fan will be stir the dust, after small time the dust is gets still at the bottom of the box. The images are taken from this time (during the dust is stirs to it gets on the bottom), we can consider all images are the hazy image but the last image is approximately optimal images. In this system if the dust is increased the laser intensity is decreased. Figures(4) and (5) illustrated the images used in this study are greed from low to high of the dust. In the figures (6,a) , (8,a) illustrated the relationship between the max. illuminance of the He-Ne laser and the SSIM for the value component in $Y C_B C_R$ color space for data images, from these figure we can see the max. illuminance of the He-Ne laser increasing with increased the SSIM due to decrease the dust. And the relationship between the max. illuminance and SSIM components was illustrate In the figures(6,b),(8,b) we can noted the contrast component is approximately remaining constant whereas the behaviors of structure and luminance are similar in the figures (6,a) and (8,a), but the SSIM is high in the contrast the figure (8,b). The figures (9,7,a,b) are illustrated the relationship between the max. illuminance and the NMSE for RGB and each component in $Y C_B C_R$ for data images , we can see the NMSE is decreasing with increased the max. illuminance in the all component, and the chromatic components C_B and C_R are more effected by the dust due to the error is high, because increasing the white light in these images.

7. CONCLUSION

In this search, we study the hazy images depending on $Y C_B C_R$ color space by using helium-neon lasers, from the result we can see the chromatic components hue follows saturation are very effected by the dust and the lightness component is low affected. And in metric SSIM for value the structure follows, the contrast are decreasing due to the dust compare with the luminance.

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Figure 3 system with is used to measure the amount of the dust that is made image is hazy

Figure 4 First group of the hazy images with different hazy levels (from maximum in a(1) to very low hazy in a(12)).

Figure 5 Second group of the hazy images with different hazy levels (from maximum in b(1) to very low hazy in b(12)).

Figure 6 The Max.illuminance as a function of SSIM for the value component in $YCbCr$ color space (in a) and (in b) the components of SSIM are (Luminance ,Contrast and Structure), for first group images.

Figure 7 Relationship between Max.illuminance and NMSE (a) for RGB component and (b) for lightness, $C_B C_R$ components, for first group images .

Figure 8 The Max.illuminance as a function of SSIM for the Value component in $Y C_B C_R$ color space (in a) and (in b) the components of SSIM are (Luminance , Contrast and Structure), for second group images.

Figure 9 Relationship between Max.illuminance and NMSE (a) for RGB component and (b) for lightness, $C_B C_R$ components, for second group images .